

DEPICTION OF STUDENTS' PERSONAGE IN THE WORLD LITERATURE

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Annotation: The article is analyzed students' personages as an object of real life descriptions. Real life is a phrase used originally in literature to distinguish between the real world and fictional or idealized worlds, and in acting to distinguish between performers and the characters they portray. More recently, it has become a popular term on the Internet to describe events, people, activities, and interactions occurring offline; or otherwise not primarily through the medium of the Internet. It is also used as a metaphor to distinguish life in a vocational setting as opposed to an academic one, or adulthood and the adult world as opposed to childhood or adolescence. The article depicts the student's character in English literature. The role, genesis, national nature, poetic-typological features and the portrait of students in the works of English literary writers, their character's features, similarities and differences. The article presents samples from English literature, analyzes and studies comparatively and typologically. The comparative study of the works of world figures analyzed in the article will have a positive impact on the development of our international literature and will promote the reading literary books and reading culture.

Keywords: portrait, image, character, student, psychological, philosophical, typological, positive, negative, protagonists

Introduction. After 1830, the spiritual climate of Western Europe changed significantly compared to the Romantic period. The subjective idealism of the Romantics was replaced by a belief in the power of reason and science, a belief in progress. Two ideas of this period define the thinking of Europeans - positivism (a

philosophical direction based on the collection of objective facts for their scientific analysis) and organism (Darwin's theory of evolution, applicable to other spheres of life). The nineteenth century was a century of rapid growth of science and technology, the rise of the social sciences, and the pursuit of scientific knowledge permeated the literature. Realist artists saw their role in literature in depicting all the richness of the phenomena of the surrounding world, the diversity of human species, i.e. 19th century science and realistic literature were imbued with the spirit of collecting and systematizing the same facts. and developing a coherent concept of reality. And the explanation of the truth is given on the basis of the principles of evolution: in the life of society and the individual, the movement of the same forces, as in nature, the mechanisms of natural selection, was evident.

By the thirties of the XIX century, a new system of social relations was finally formed. It was a bourgeois system in which everyone was firmly attached to a particular socio-class environment, that is, the period of romantic 'freedom', 'disturbance' of man had passed. In classical bourgeois society, the belonging of a person to a certain class emerged as the unchanging law of existence and, accordingly, became the principle of the artistic development of life. Therefore, realists use the discoveries of romance in the field of psychology, but write historically accurate, new concepts about man in modern life. For realists, man is primarily determined by the socio-historical environment, while realism is based on the principle of socio-class determinism.

Materials and methods. The object of the research was selected works that meet the image of a student in the plot. In particular, Razumov "Under the western eyes" by Evelyn Vaugh, Paul Pennyfezer Evelyn Waugh's "Decline and fall", Charlotte Tom Wolf's "I am Charlotte Simons", Richard Paypen and other students Donna Tart's "The secret history" in Anglo-American literature, Saidiy and Munishon in A. Qahhor's novel "Sarob" in Uzbek literature, Mahkam and Gavhar in P. Kadyrov's novel "Three Roots", Azimjon and Ormonjon in Sh. Kholmiraev's

"Uzbek character", Jura in Ghulam's story "Yodgor", Muzaffar and Munnavar Utkir Hoshimov's "Between Two Doors" ("Ikki eshik orasi"), several types of students P. Kadyrov's "Students" personages were addressed.

Methodology may be visualized as a spectrum from a predominantly quantitative approach towards a predominantly qualitative approach. Although a methodology may conventionally sit specifically within one of these approaches, researchers may blend approaches in answering their research objectives and so have methodologies that are multimethod and/or interdisciplinary.

Overall, a methodology does not set out to provide solutions - it is therefore, not the same as a method. Instead, a methodology offers a theoretical perspective for understanding which method, set of methods, or best practices can be applied to the research question(s) at hand.

Methodology of the research is deep typologically analyzing, identifying the differentiate students' images of the world, Anglo-American and Uzbek literature works. Determine similarity and difference of students' personage in the world and Uzbek literature.

Discussion and the results. In world literature, the student and student period is characterized in the works of several writers, the personal life of students, their university life is skillfully depicted in a realistic, colorful way, and student life is embodied directly the reader.

In world literature, student life is characterized differently in the works of the world literature writers.

1. Involvement of students in crime. For example: F. Raskolnikov's crime in Dostoevsky's "Crime and Punishment". (Death of an old woman). The murder of Khaldin, a student in Joseph Conrad's "Under the western eye". (Death of the Prime Minister). In Donna Tart's "Secret History", we can find in the works of writers a group of students who commit crimes.

2.The economic disadvantage of student youth in world literature. Financial difficulties. In the character of students we can meet orphaned or otherwise orphaned students. In Dostoevsky's "Crime and Punishment", Raskolnikov had no breadwinners other than his mother and sister. "You know how much we love you: I and the world have no one but you, you are our soul, you are our only hope.[3:38] His mother was barely sending money from her pension to her son. This lack of resources also forced Raskolnikov to drop out of the university. Perhaps he would not have been in such a situation if his financial situation was adequate." "If only you knew how I felt when I heard that you hadn't been to university for months, that you hadn't even taught, that you had no money left! What could I do for you with my pension of one hundred and twenty roubles in a year?." [3:39] In this play, the author describes the student's marital status in a very sad way. Even for the money, Raskolnikov's mother says she was forced to marry her daughter to a rich man.

One of the best works of world literature is the character of Razumov in the work of the English writer Joseph Conard, entitled "Under the western eyes" . Razumov, a student at St. Petersburg University, was a lonely student. Despite the fact that he did not have a family, there were many people who supported him, as the author states that he came from a family of aristocrats. "It was believed that Mr. Razumov was the son of an archpriest and was under the auspices of some high-ranking aristocrat, possibly from the same remote province where he was from." [1: 225]

Razumov doesn't even feel the need for money at all because he was receiving financial help from someone. "Razumov received enough money from his adoptive parents," he said. That money was enough to support him. " [1:225] Razumov never regrets his loneliness because we can always meet him among the rich aristocrats. Most of his acquaintances were friends, princes, rich people. His main goal was to study and he met with various professors in order to achieve his goal. The character of Rastinyak in Honoré de Balzac's family was much more hopeful for him, and

everyone supported him. “Eugene de Rastinyak — that was the name of the young man — was one of those young men who learned to work out of need, and such young men knew from a young age that all the hope of family members was in themselves and weighing all the benefits of science and being one of the first to benefit from the development of future society, adapt all the knowledge they have acquired to the development of society, and strive to create for themselves as bright a future as possible.” [5:18] Similar to Rastinyak's image and Razumov's, they did not suffer much from money, but they were among the nobility, in their circle, and, of course, they did not feel much need. However, Razumov had a high level of education and was not interested in the material world. Rastinyak, on the other hand, always wanted to be rich, and so we used to meet him in conversations at aristocratic events.

The protagonist of Donna Tart's “The secret history” (“Taynaya istoriya”) was eager to enroll in school, but his father would not help with funding. He lived with the help of well-off student friends throughout his student days as well. “The next few months were quite stressful for me. My father objected me going to college and said he would not give me any money. I called the college lobby and told them I didn't have the money but I really wanted to study. They agreed to reimburse me for my travel expenses if I accepted the terms of several scholarships. [10;16]

It is clear that one of the student heroes was suffering from financial hardship and the other was living at someone else's expense.

3. The works also depict students 'chaotic lifestyles, with writers portraying them as hooligans rather than students. When Charlotte Simmons, a smart, humble and simple girl from a simple family, a round excellent student from a small town, entered one of the most elite universities in the United States, most students were interested in sex, alcohol, and a light lifestyle.

To write this novel, Tom Wolf spent four years specifically on campus. He puts the world he observes on paper. The cute girl named Charlotte Simmons. He

grew up in the small town of Sparta, and despite the fact that the city was far from civilization, he was able to enter Dupont to study. Charlotte has a great mind, dreams of becoming famous and superior to her ordinary peers. Miss Simmons was brought up in a strict hand because her moral values are above all, she is clean and spotless and all men can feel it. She is beautiful and charming and of course achieves academic success.

“...After all, if you look closely, at the university, students were swearing at each other, beating, and the administration was always insulting them for constantly using alcohol, herbs, cocaine, "ecstasy" ... and in that case all sorts of idiots, excellent students, aspiring graduate students, teachers, various minorities - punks, metalheads, homosexuals, lesbians, bisexuals, sadomasochists, blacks, Latinos, Indians - some from India, others from reservations, in general, people like Hoyt accused of racism, sexism, classism - what the hell is this? - chauvinism, anti-Semitism, far-right views, homophobia ... Yes, views on different animals were firmly established at this university ... ” [2;68] It was a real-life depiction of the famous Dupont University students by the author.

In the works of Uzbek literature, on the contrary, the writers are widely described and described in the works of love, student-teacher relations, hatred and anger, patriotism, the difficulties of the student period, bribery.

In Uzbek literature we can find different images that differ from each other in terms of intellect, worldview, dress code, portraiture. The image of the student has a special place in fiction. It illuminates the worldview, behavior, material and spiritual world, dreams and aspirations of the youth of their time. Through this image, the future of the society in which that student lives is indicated.

1. Student-teacher relationship. Of course, where there is the character of a student, there is also the character of teachers and tutors who teach them directly. Their relationship is directly formal, friendly, like a parent, sincere. Along with these qualities, the theme of love between student and teacher is also imprinted

in the works. This theme first appeared in Uzbek literature in the twentieth century in the poetic drama "Atlas" by Usman Nasir. Later, this theme was widely covered in Ulugbek Hamdam's "Sabo and Samandar". The difference between these two works is that in "Sabo and Samandar" the teacher and the student girl are worthy of each other. But from a social point of view, the teacher is average. "Samandar grew up to be a shivering, steamy, middle-aged man, whose whole appearance was so clear from hard work. But it was not the qualities that struck him, but the deep and sharp gaze of his sunken eyes, his eagle-nosed nose, his gypsum-covered lips, and the proud and sad look on his face." [12;80]

His mother, who grew up as an orphan, raised her child alone. So he worked hard and entered the study on his own so that it would not be difficult for him. " – If there are simple numbers, why do you always clean yourself like that, go out at night and pick cotton, as you do during the day? Even for simple numbers, can a person take himself out of the fire and hit the top ?! Samandar did not know what to say. Aziza didn't look at what he had been doing since he came to his senses, he didn't notice it, he was stunned ... Then he reluctantly explained the reason:– I need to work harder and save money to enter the university, Aziza" [12;66]

But Sabo is the only child of a family. But she is a beautiful girl, even if she is alone. Polite, intelligent and beautiful. "Looking at Sabo's wealth, his brown hair around his white neck, his long eyelashes, his beautiful nose, his pouty lips, Samandar tried to memorize all of this in the highest and warmest poetic novelty." [12;106]

The love in his heart is also pure and fiery. "Sabo's state was similar to Samandar's. For the first time in months, his face smiled ... Even when he laughed, he smiled happily. It is as if there is not a century left of grief, of the bitter days and months of the lines drawn on the passes. " [12;110]

Love is so deep in his heart that he doesn't even reach his friends' minds. It never occurs to her that her parents would not marry her to such a man. "Samandar

aka is a good man, handsome, honest .. But they will not give you to your grandchildren, Sabo!" What are you doing, he himself! [12;111]

Sabo is such an anxious Aryan girl that she becomes a victim of her father's debt and doesn't get out of her parents' opinion. "The mother wanted to tell her daughter that no matter how hard she tried, there were no other options for her daughter to get married her father's friend son. Otherwise his father will have no job and money. [12;145]

Sabo's father also considers Samandar to be unworthy of Saba at all, and even going to him we can see how much they don't match, his father ignores Samandar "–Shut up! Stupid! Saidkamol aka angrily punched the table.–Don't tell anything. I spit on your love! What, does it feed your stomach? Do you know what my daughter ate and what she wore, you know, naked! Your monthly teaching salary is not enough to Sabo's dress Who are you that wanted to marry minister's daughter. I know the purpose of people like you. Your aim is only money nothing else. [12;157]

Unfortunately, their love ends tragically. Although the two lovers are married separately, they do not share each other's thoughts, loves and feelings. They never forgot each other, on the contrary, they did not chase each other's visors. Sabo always thought about Samandar and died by heart attack. Samandar, on the other hand, always lived and walked with Sabo's imagination. He died in an accident.

In "Atlas", we can see a completely different picture, a different interpretation. The lover (teacher) there is deceitful, selfish, and stupid. He is a victim of his own uncontrollable feelings and desires. "Know Atlason, love is in my heart. Is there a compassion in your heart that plays like a dove, even if it's a genie? I didn't know, I saw you, the power broke my heart like a mirror. I saw you, the power crushed my existence. Saw you ...

Girl, girl. how I want to hug her.." [13;203]

Nozim Kamolov speaks completely against his position, his teaching status, and does the opposite. In return for his lust, the young student deceives the girl and destroys her future.

Atlas is a beautiful, young, beautiful student girl who still does not know the ups and downs of life. The lover flies at the teacher's words and recognizes her as his wife. "He is not what I thought he was," he said. The man you walk with now says san. He beats, insults, insults ... Mother: Bride, speak attentively, the woman's seed did not come from Urgut, we did not bring you as a bride's wedding with a dream, you came in with your own feet, she scolds. I can't go if I tell Qumri to go. I have a child I didn't tell you about..."[13; 212]

The docent is not at all interested in the future of the poor girl's fate, but rather tells her that it is the property of a lust. He has no regrets at all. This teacher is not worthy of his position, to educate young people at all. On the contrary, such ugly people have no right to teach in higher education.

In these two completely different works, one depicts pure love, while the other depicts deception, the loneliness of lustful youth. "In Sabo and Samandar, Samandar is a teacher of literature and a young lover, while Nozim Kamolov in Atlas is a much older and associate professor. It is also possible to understand what kind of love can be between them through the age difference of the protagonists of the work. Through these works, our two writers have combined such themes as pure love, student-teacher relations, educating young people, protecting them from evil. I think this does a great educational job for the reader.

Students are having children without getting married. "Between Two Doors ", the student protagonists (Munavar and Muzaffar) became pregnant as a result of their close relationship during the cotton period. But the fact that they could not have a wedding because they were breastfeeding brothers and sisters ended tragically (death of Munawwar).

About the hardships of Atlas girl and Orzumand boy in Usman Nasir's poetic drama "Atlas" during his student period. At first, Orzumand does not understand the essence of the professor's words to Atlas about his youth and love. Entering their conversation, Orzumand is jealous of the professor, suspecting him of falling in love with Atlas. Even because of this jealousy, the professor misunderstands every move and begins to feel like an unjust victim. He even finds a mistake in the professor's words during a lecture one day and tries to embarrass him. With this move, the student offends Atlas as well as his friends. After that, Atlas becomes disillusioned with Orzumand and ignores him. Orzumand also gets angry with Atlas, walks away from him and leaves the girl alone. Taking advantage of this situation, a new teacher, Associate Professor Nozim Kamolov, deceives the student by telling her sweet words, the words of great people about love, thus convincing her of his "love" and misleading her. As a result, the future of the girl who becomes a victim of his lust is ruined. Kamolov is not interested in the girl's future at all. "You came and went like one of those I saw ... You were only and only the property of lust. I was looking for nothing but you. Nazim doesn't need anything in time! He came to live, to enjoy, to seek his own happiness, to seek his own self," she said facelessly. [13;215].

Nazim, a cunning fake lover, considers himself a master "traveler" and is proud of it. He violates the honor of Atlas, does not marry her. After achieving his evil goal, his lust, he ignores Atlas. Even his mother insults Atlas. She does not recognize her child. As a result, Atlas leaves their home.

In the drama, the hesitations between the very simple, ordinary student girl Atlas and the lyrical experiences and feelings of Orzumand, who falls into the trap of curious, youthful ignorance, are revealed in the scenes of a sharp struggle. When Orzumand realizes that he has lost Atlas as a result of his curiosity and unreasonable jealousy, his teacher as his father returns to his lover again through the advice of an old professor. A more cordial teacher-disciple relationship continues between them and the old and loving professor.

Farida and Zokir's mistakes in Pirimkul Kadyrov's "Three Roots". "After the student party, Zakir followed Farida home and the two slept together because no one else was there. Zokir had champagne in his pocket as he knew it before." [4;421 After this, Zokir's attitude towards Farida changed. He always developed a habit of arguing over nothing under the pretext of something. Tired of such quarrels, Farida decided to cancel the wedding despite being pregnant. "Farida's head was very upset and she couldn't eat. So go on Zakir drunk complaints: violation of the wedding, and now Makhmudov? he argued. As a result of a series of ups and downs, Farida eventually fell ill and lost her fetus.

The period of cotton age. It is no exaggeration to say that the cotton period was one of the most important periods in the life of students, a part of the student period. This period has been skillfully described by our writers. For example, in "Between Two Doors.". The cotton period is also well described in this play. Student nutrition during the cotton period. Making soup and tea for students from donkey watering water. "Ur Come on! I said, squeezing Munawwar.–Let's not run out of pasta soup!–I don't drink–Munawwar suddenly started shooting.–Let the pasta soup rest on top.–Why?–Haven't you seen!–Munawwar shakes his hand angrily.–Donkey was watered there! He takes water from that bucket, makes tea, and puts water on the food!" [7;539]

Students make plov together. " Suddenly everyone started to work. Knives and carrot planks were found from the village houses." [7;540]

The story "Character of Uzbeks" describes the long-term involvement of journalism students (now TSNU) in the cotton harvest during the cotton season, often taking them to Mirzachul, and the conditions for students. "I wanted to get out faster. Ormon aka's words and questions touched my heart ... What? E, darling, do you think you don't understand me? Ha-ha! My brother Ormonjon was right ... There is another side to the issue: we ourselves were not satisfied. One of them was

carrying half a kilo of sugar, the other was stealing, someone was stealing meat from someone's bowl ... I can't say..”[11;68]

The conditions in which the students lived, such as the laundry, the washing conditions, the theft of things there, the begging, were vitally expressed. “It started to rain continuously. We were without food for two days. Even so, many children were in debt. Gradually, our ambassadors developed a habit of wandering the streets of the village: at night they bring dozens and fifteen melons at a time. The next day there was a quarrel at the headquarters: someone complained that a thief had broken into his yard ... So we started to learn about the theft..”[11;69]

1. Bribery. They work hard to get into the institute. They also carefully prepare for exams. But Sharifjon's knowledge gives him a lot of reasons for the entrance exams. He passes the oral exam well but makes too many mistakes in his written essay. "It was an essay I wrote about Gulnara and Yulchi in my own handwriting. It was fixed with a red pencil, drawn in such a way that it looked like a flower blanket, and not a single sentence was left untouched by the pencil. ” [14:31]

Even though Sharifjon's father's friend Sulaymon aka Sharifjon told his mother that this was a bad thing, they did it anyway. They still didn't know what the consequences would be. “ I am not against Sharif's study. I'm just saying let him study, let him be an engineer, just don't go that way! -said Sulaymon aka. "I'm just saying, if he is an engineer or a scientist, let him will be honestly" Well, don't you have something else to say? Goodbye! ” [14:34] It is no exaggeration to say that Sulaymon aka's statement will be a model for all parents. When Sharifjon found out that his essay had been replaced by Muqaddas's essay, he tried his best to correct the mistake, and even though he had heard bad words from the dean, he ignored them and began to correct the mistake. “Who is dishonest? Is it you or me?said he dean, his eyes twinkling with hatred. "They call you dishonest!" Do you understand? I didn't know what to say, because he was right! ” [14:42] He was well aware of how ugly he had become. He even tried to expose those involved in the

case. But he thought of his mother. Because his stepfather was involved to this event. He did not do this to maintain family peace. “Yes, my problem is solved! I said, glaring angrily at his smooth, round face, and at the gray eyes that glistened under his gold spectacles. - But I wanted to talk to the people who solved the problem! I came to expose them! I will expose! Do you understand my purpose now? ” [14:43]

After this incident, the fate of these two teenagers falls apart, and neither of them has the opportunity to become a student. "It simply came to my notice then. Love is a sacred feeling. It requires purity. Muqaddas had left me and my love and opened my eyes. "It simply came to my notice then. Love is a sacred feeling. It requires purity. The saint had left me and my love and opened my eyes.." [14:45] writers believed in the effectiveness of their critiques, that society believed in self-improvement, reform, and the inevitability of progress.

Conclusion Perceptions of human character among realists have also changed. A special character for the Romantics was the subjective property of the individual; the protagonist of a realistic work is always a unique product of the interaction of historical process and specific (biological, individual, random) situations, so realists understand each person's life experience as unique and valuable by this rarity itself and, on the other hand, each person's life experience is a universal, universal interest because it has repetitive, universal features. Herein lies the basis of the realistic doctrine of tourism, the basis of the realistic classification.

The realists inherited the inherent dignity of the human personality they invented directly from the Romantics, but they established this personality for a particular place, time, and environment. Realist art is democratic - realists first brought to the stage a “little man” who was not previously considered an interesting object for literature, and restored their rights. Realistic literature is generally imbued with a spirit of optimism: when criticizing modern society, realist

In both literature works (Uzbek and foreign literature), one can come across with the student of bad and good manner, intelligent or misbehaving, knowledgeable or stupid, courageous or uncourageous, poor and rich

1. Character in world literature works are given as follows: addict, alcohol, homosexuals, lonely, criminal, greedy for money etc. The world literature writers also describe educated, skilled, kind, friendly protagonists.

2. Students' characters in Uzbek literature are educated, skilled, hospitable, patriot, hardworking, intelligent. While we can also meet light-hearted, disrespectful, bad mannered and criminal student protagonists as well.

Deep understanding of truth, correct instinct of truth, simplicity, artistic depiction of characters, richness of content, enduring charm of presentation, poetic language, deep knowledge of human heart and modern society, breadth and boldness of brush, power and strength of spirit, luxurious fantasy, aesthetic life abundance, originality - these are the qualities that make this work a whole new world of art. All this forces us to pay full attention to it and to acquaint our readers deeply with it, to reveal the riches it contains in aesthetic life.

Finally, understanding the deepest layer, one of the ways to penetrate the protagonist's inner world is the work itself: individual episodes, approaching similarity and contrast of scenes, repetition of plot situations (plot level or presence of external plot elements of the plot, such as biblical legends, parables and other episodes included).

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